

CRYPTOGRAMMA (L.) R. BR. EX HOOK. IN THE FLORA OF RUSSIA

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Dataset on GBIF

Access to the dataset

Description

A critical revision of herbarium collections of the genus *Cryptogramma* in the LE, MW, ALTB, NSK, NS, TK, SVER, VLA, KRAS herbariums made it possible to conduct a complete review of this genus in Russia. The work carried out made it possible to clarify the systematic characters and identify the exact distribution of species in the area.

Geographic scope

Territory of the Russian Federation

Bibliography

Vaganov A.V. 2009. The review of genus *Cryptogramma* (*Cryptogrammaceae*) in flora of Russia. *Botanicheskiy zhurnal*. No. 12. C: 1821–1835.

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Endpoints <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/archive.do?r=cryptogramma> (Darwin Core Archive) <http://altb.asu.ru/ipt/eml.do?r=cryptogramma> (EML)
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